

MULTIPATH TREE-STRUCTURED VECTOR QUANTIZERS

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ABSTRACT

Tree-structured vector quantization (TSVQ) is a popular mean of avoiding the exponential complexity of full-search vector quantizers. We present two new design algorithms for TSVQ in which more than one path can be chosen at each internal node. The two algorithms differ on the way the paths are chosen. In the first algorithm the number of paths is fixed and the encoding is similar to the M-algorithm for delayed decision coders. In the second algorithm, the paths are chosen adaptively at each node, according to a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbor rule. We show the performances of the two algorithms on an AR(1) gaussian process, and observe that the adaptive method is the best one. Those methods allow near full-search performances at a fraction of the complexity cost.

1 INTRODUCTION

In standard vector quantization (VQ, [4]), a discrete input signal is decomposed into a sequence of k -dimensional vectors and each input vector is mapped onto a so-called *codevector* belonging to a finite set of representative vectors, the *codebook*. We will use the notations $\mathcal{P} = \{y_i : i = 1 \dots n\} \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ for the codebook. The output of the quantization is a sequence of index belonging to $\mathcal{I} = \{1 \dots n\}$, and the choice of the best codevector, that is the mapping $\alpha : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathcal{I}$, is usually made according to a minimum distance criteria, for instance $\alpha(x) = \arg \min_i d(x, y_i)$, where $d(x, y_i) = \|x - y_i\|^2$.

Codebook generation methods are most of the time derived from the generalized Lloyd algorithm, which consists of alternate local optimizations of the encoder and the decoder. The most widely known variant of the GLA is probably the Linde-Buzo-Gray (LBG, [6]) algorithm.

The problem of implementing the mapping α is in its simplest form— a nearest neighbor search problem, which is quite costly in terms of computation time. A

classical solution for this problem is to use a constrained structure for the codebook, so that the search can be performed efficiently. The codevector found is not optimal, but the degradation in quality is expected to be small. The tree structure [1] [7] is a well-known example of such a constraint.

In tree-structured vector quantization (TSVQ), a hierarchy of codevectors is built, in which each codevector on level l is either in a leaf node, and will serve as the final representation of the encoded vector, or in an internal node, with a number of sons in level $l + 1$. The encoder follows a path from the root node of the tree, and selects at each node the nearest codevector. The design for a balanced tree (in which all leaves are in the same level) is usually derived from the GLA. One can also build unbalanced trees, which are more efficient than balanced ones and sometimes even better than full-search vector quantizers. Strategies for constructing unbalanced trees belong to two families : pruned TSVQ and grown TSVQ [7], and also require some GLA iterations when splitting a leaf node.

We denote a TSVQ by $\mathcal{T}$ and the set of nodes associated to the l th level of the tree $\mathcal{T}$ by the symbol $\mathcal{P}_{\mathcal{T}}^l$. b is used to denote the fan-out of the tree (considered as constant here). We deliberately use the term “node” for both a tree node and the codevector associated to it. The codevectors are written y_i , and the sons of node i are $\{son_1(i), \dots, son_b(i)\}$.

2 MULTIPATH TREE-STRUCTURED VECTOR QUANTIZATION

In this work, we study a variant of classical tree-structured vector quantization called *multipath tree-structured vector quantization* (MP-TSVQ). The main idea is as follows : instead of choosing one path at each node, we pick up many of them, according to some heuristic function, and follow them simultaneously in the lower levels. The choice is iterated at each node down to the leaf level, in which we simply choose the nearest codevector among the selected ones. This technique has been first introduced in [2] in the framework of video coding with good coding performances improve-

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ment.

A formal description of the general encoding algorithm is given in algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 A general encoding algorithm for MP-TSVQ

x is the input vector
 S is a set of codevector indices
 $\mathcal{T}$ is the tree
 $S \leftarrow \{ \text{root node index} \}$
for each level of $\mathcal{T}$ **do**
 $S \leftarrow$ selected nodes in S
 $S \leftarrow \cup_{i \in S} \cup_{r=1}^b \{ \text{son}_r(i) \}$
end for
return $\text{argmin}_{i \in S} d(x, y_i)$

The basic idea behind this is that by choosing only one path, you can miss a better codevector located in another path. In a way, the standard search is a greedy approximation of a backtracking nearest neighbor search, and the multipath search is an enhancement of this greedy method which could be used when some additional computational load is acceptable.

Also note that MP-TSVQ is a generalization of both TSVQ and full-search VQ : TSVQ is obtained when only the nearest node is chosen at each level, while full-search VQ is equivalent to a MP-TSVQ in which all paths are selected.

We will ask ourselves what could be the best path selection method, and how the tree should be designed according to this selection method. As a beginning of answer for the first question, we have tested the two simple path selection methods described hereunder.

2.1 m -path Quantization

An example of m -path search is given in Fig. 1. In m -path searching, we simply select the m nearest neighbors of the input vector as candidates for the next tree level. The choice of m is of course empirical, but should be made according to the computational load we want to obtain. The computational cost of such a coding process is directly proportional to m . More precisely, we perform $O(m.b.k.\log_b n)$ floating point operations for each encoded vector.

This algorithm is similar to the M-algorithm in the framework of delayed decision encoders [5].

The problem of this method is that the number of paths followed at each level is constant, so it may sometimes select paths that are unlikely to be useful (when the input is clearly much closer to one codevector), and also miss some paths that could have been interesting (when the input is close to many codevectors).

2.2 $(1 + \epsilon)$ -multipath Quantization

The second method tries to solve the selection problem in a more adaptive way than the previous one. It uses the following definition :

Figure 1: m -path search : black dots represent the two nearest neighbors at each level

Figure 2: Black dots are the $(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbors of x , with $\epsilon = 1$

Definition 1 ($(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbors) Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ denote a finite set of vectors, x a vector, and y^* the nearest neighbor of x in S , then $y \in S$ is a $(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbor of x iff

$$d(x, y) \leq (1 + \epsilon).d(x, y^*) \tag{1}$$

An illustration of this definition is given in Fig. 2. In $(1 + \epsilon)$ -multipath quantization we select, among the current candidates, all the $(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbors of the input. The choice is intuitively satisfying : the number of $(1 + \epsilon)$ -nearest neighbors is varying according to the distance from the input x to its nearest neighbor. If this distance is small, the number of selected paths will be small too.

The choice of the value of ϵ is made empirically. We can imagine a bisection algorithm similar to the one used in rate/distortion optimization methods for the choice of the lagrangian multiplier. We can however measure accurately the computational load of a quantizer designed with a fixed ϵ by computing the average number of paths followed at each level. This measure will be used in our experiments to compare the performances of the selection methods with a fixed encoding complexity.

3 A PROCEDURE FOR BALANCED MP-TSVQ DESIGN

The tree in a MP-TSVQ should be designed according to a defined path selection method. The training vectors have to follow exactly the same paths as the encoded vectors, which is not the case in the method described in [2].

The generalization of the classical TSVQ design method to MP-TSVQ is quite straightforward. Unlike the standard TSVQ design algorithm, a MP-TSVQ can only be designed in a breadth-first way. A set of “available paths” is associated to each training vector, and updated at each level in the following way :

- select the nodes according to the selection rule,
- replace each selected node in the set by its sons.

In the unbalanced case some nodes in the set may be leaves, so we simply eliminate them. For simplification, we will assume in the following that the tree is balanced.

Algorithm 2 is a pseudo-code description of the design strategy. The symbol S_t^j denotes the set of available paths for the training vector x_t at level j , and R_i is the training vector subset associated to the codevector y_i (that is, the Monte-Carlo approximation of the quantization cell of y_i .)

Algorithm 2 Balanced MP-TSVQ design algorithm

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path set initialization
 $S_t^0 \leftarrow \{ \text{root node index} \}, \forall t$ 
for each level  $l$  do
  repeat
     $R_i \leftarrow \emptyset, \forall i = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{P}_T^l|$ 
    encoder optimization
    for each training vector  $x_t$  do
       $i \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{i \in S_t^l} d(x_t, y_i)$ 
       $R_i \leftarrow R_i \cup \{x_t\}$ 
    end for
    decoder optimization
    for each codevector  $y_i \in \mathcal{P}_T^l$  do
       $y_i \leftarrow \text{centroid}(R_i)$ 
    end for
  until convergence
  set updates
  for each training vector index  $t$  do
     $S_t^l \leftarrow \text{selected nodes in } S_t^l$ 
     $S_t^{l+1} \leftarrow \cup_{i \in S_t^l} \cup_{r=1}^b \{ \text{son}_r(i) \}$ 
  end for
end for

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4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiments have been performed on a synthetic Gauss-Markov process blocked into 16-dimensional vectors. The tree is a complete binary tree of height 8. Figure 4

Figure 3: Examples of sets of codevectors associated to a training vector during the design of the tree

Figure 4: Results obtained with a 8-level tree on a AR(1) process with correlation 0.9 blocked into 16-dimensional vectors

Figure 5: Effects of design mismatch

shows the graph of the signal-to-quantization noise ratio vs. the average number of paths followed for the two path selection methods described before. Note that the number of paths is not always an integer—even for the m -path case—because the total number of selected codevectors is divided by the number of levels, and only one codevector is selected at the leaf level.

We can see that the distortion decreases at a decreasing speed for both methods, and that the $(1 + \epsilon)$ -multipath quantization is clearly better than the fixed-path method, excepted for a high number of paths, in which case they have, however, comparable performances. The full-search performances are nearly obtained for a 5-path search, with a complexity reduction factor equal to 3.2.

Another advantage of the adaptive selection method is that any point on the curve may be reached, unlike in the m -path technique.

Other experiments were performed in order to validate the design method described in algorithm 2. We used the $(1 + \epsilon)$ selection method, and encoded a test set taken from the Gauss-Markov distribution with two different encoders :

1. a multipath encoder used on a tree designed with the same ϵ value,
2. a multipath encoder used on a simple TSVQ, i.e. on a MP-TSVQ designed with $\epsilon = 0$.

The results are presented in Fig. 5, and clearly show the advantage of using the design parameters corresponding to the path selection method of the encoder. Actually the second encoding cannot encode better than a full search in a suboptimal codebook, a limit which appears clearly on the graph. On the other hand, correct training leads to optimal full search performances when ϵ is increased.

5 CONCLUSION

Since MP-TSVQ is an intermediate between full-search VQ and TSVQ, it may be used as a fast full-search codebook design method. We could for example directly use the MP-TSVQ codebook as a full-search VQ codebook, or use the MP-TSVQ codebook as a starting point for the GLA algorithm.

Another interesting issue is the application of multipath design to variable-rate TSVQ. One could try for instance to minimize Lagrangian distortion measure, or apply stopping rules in order to cut out subtrees. The existing variable-rate design methods are, however, not directly applicable to the MP-TSVQ described here, because of its intrinsic breadth-first nature.

TSVQ structures can also serve as a basis for efficient multi-resolution codes [3].

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